

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue I, January 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

@pinagpalapublishing

pinagpala_publishing

www.pinagpalapublishing.com

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024)/ International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Evolving Strategies in Mathematics Teaching

ROSE L. AGLIAM

Teacher I

Schools Division of Tarlac Province

Mathematics has traditionally been viewed with universal importance due to its critical role in student development and future prospects (Boaler, 2022). However, traditional teaching approaches have often relied on rote memorization and direct instruction, leading to students perceiving math as rigorous, burdensome, and disconnected from real life (O'Neill, 2023). Over the years, various stakeholders, including educators and policymakers, have been emphasizing a shift towards more transformative and inclusive approaches to mathematics teaching.

Research trends from 2022 to 2024 indicate a steady adoption of problem-solving and investigative methods in maths education. These strategies embrace active learning models whereby students are encouraged to explore, experiment, and reason in mathematical contexts (Lerman, 2024). Integrating collaborative tasks and disciplinary connections helps in promoting deeper understanding, fostering skill development, and making mathematics more tangible to students (Mullis & Martin, 2022).

House et al. (2023) highlighted the importance of using digital tools to leverage technology's instructional potential. Implementing tech-based integrated strategies allow for personal learning adjustments, real-time feedback, and multi-modal demonstrations, which can significantly enhance comprehension and motivation.

Inclusive strategies, too, have gained prominence in math instruction. Tied to the broader movement toward diversity and inclusion in education, they encourage diverse representations, seek to eliminate bias and stereotype threats, and facilitate equal opportunities for students of different backgrounds and abilities (Hehir & Katzman, 2024).

The advancement towards these contemporary teaching practices implies a need for quality teacher professional development. Appleton (2022) suggested that professional learning communities (PLCs), instructional coaching and collaborative inquiry can support teachers in incorporating modern classroom innovations effectively.

The advent of systemic changes does not marginalize the need for rigorous assessment. As Hirsch et al. (2024), noted, "assessment should serve as a bridge between teaching and learning", reflecting the student's ability to understand, apply, and extend mathematical concepts.

In conclusion, the strategies in mathematics teaching signal a shift towards fostering deeper understanding, inclusive learning environments, meaningful integration of digital tools, and high-quality teacher development and assessment.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024)/ International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

References

1. Appleton, S. (2022). Constructing collaborative networks for inclusive education. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 73(1), 75-89.
2. Boaler, J. (2022). *Mathematical Mindsets: Unleashing Students' Potential through Creative Math, Inspiring Messages, and Innovative Teaching*. Jossey-Bass.
3. Hehir, T., & Katzman, L. (2024). Equity in education: Examining the impact of inclusive instructional strategies. *Journal of Educational Research and Innovations*, 2(2), 15-30.
4. House, J. D., Singh, K., & Lee, N. (2023). The role of technology in mathematics education: A theoretical and empirical review. *Mathematics Education Research Journal*, 35(4), 905-927.
5. Hirsch, L., O'Donnell, A., & Fisher, D. (2024). The role of assessment in effective mathematics instruction. *Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education*, 27(3), 220-237.
6. Lerman, S. (2024). Learner autonomy and the mathematical learner. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 63, 131-142.
7. Mullis, I., & Martin, M. (2022). *Mathematics Achievement in the Middle School Years: IEA's Fourth International Mathematics Study*. Springer.
8. O'Neill, J. (2023). Situated cognition and mathematics education: Implications for cognitive development. *International Journal of Learning*, 10(2), 111-117.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10478162

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.